

AI in Higher Education: Does Not Help, Might Hurt

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January 17th 2024

Abstract

It was observed within the Bentley University Fall 2023 Semester Introductory Finance curriculum that applying ChatGPT-4 in a tutoring environment coincided with significantly worse student outcomes compared to no tutoring, Finance tutoring and general non-Finance tutoring. This study leveraged a population of 408 freshman and sophomore undergraduates that opted-in via an IRB-approved Informed Consent process. The results demonstrate statistical significance under standard testing metrics, and confirm several well-established principles related to the effects of tutoring and the importance of instructor for learning outcomes. A causal channel of AI interfering with learning as a ‘cognitive prosthesis’ is proposed for further investigation.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, pedagogy, higher education, finance, learning outcomes

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Conflict of interest disclosure statement

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On December 17th 2023, the author accepted the invitation to serve on Bentley University's Artificial Intelligence Task Force in Education, Research and Business Operations. The findings of this paper are independent from the work of the Task Force. Any opinions expressed in this work are those of the author and not of Bentley University. All work on the study is self-financed with operational support from Bentley University. The author has no other conflicts to declare.

Artificial intelligence statement

This paper is entirely human-generated with the exception of the use of Microsoft-OpenAI's ChatGPT-4 for citation formatting and R version 4.2.2 low-level coding contributions. There are no Large Language Model or other Artificial Intelligence-related technology direct content contributions. Artificial Intelligence was in no way used to collect data or monitor student activity for the study.

Acknowledgements

The “Artificial Intelligence and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education” study could not have happened without the advice and support of the following individuals and groups: Fred Ledley (Bentley University – Head of Bentley Research Council), Kartik Raman (Bentley University – Chair, Finance Department), Anthony Kiszewski (Bentley University – Chair, Institutional Review Board), Claude Cicchetti (Bentley University – Course Coordinator, FI-118), Gaurav Shah (Bentley University – Head of the Academic Technology Center), Maria Skaletsky (Bentley University – Academic Technology Center), Aaron Jackson (Bentley University – Associate Dean), Edward Kim (Bentley University – Mathematics Department), Kuwait College of Science and Technology, Catherina Carlson, the Bentley University Finance Department FI-118 Faculty, the Bentley University FDS Fall 2023 freshman AI Seminar participants, and most importantly the student tutors from the Bentley University Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance.

1. Introduction

This paper details the “Artificial Intelligence and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education” study (“the study”) that ran during the Fall 2023 Semester (September 5th 2023 to December 20th 2023) at Bentley University and analyzes its results. Artificial Intelligence (AI), in particular Large Language Models (LLMs) such as Microsoft-OpenAI’s ChatGPT, has the potential to either severely disrupt or materially improve the education industry; it is this papers’ finding that risks outweigh the benefits of moving too quickly in academic mass-adoption of LLM technology in its current state. The study was run on an opt-in basis with freshman and sophomore undergraduates across all eighteen sections of required Introductory Finance curriculum and mapped academic outcomes over the course of the semester onto use of AI¹ in a tutoring environment. The study leveraged the subscription version of Microsoft-OpenAI’s ChatGPT-4, as delivered via peer-tutoring resources in the Howard A. Winer Learning Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance (LEAF).² The conclusions of this study, while cautioning against full causal inference, suggest that students are using AI as “cognitive prostheses” (Edyburn, 2003, p. 76) to replace, rather than support, learning in the business curriculum.

Education has been described as one of the fields most heavily impacted by the recent COVID-19 pandemic (Brooks & Springer, 2023). Similarly, AI poses existential challenges to the current US Higher Education model across a variety of different functions that are core to its

¹ For the purposes of this paper, though “AI” is used to reference a wide range of technologies it predominantly refers to the Microsoft-OpenAI ChatGPT-4 product and similar LLM competitor offerings. More information behind this choice of technology is given in Section 3.

² The author of this paper is the principal investigator in the “Artificial Intelligence and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education” and has been the Faculty Director of the LEAF since Fall 2022 as University Service.

objectives, including content delivery, academic integrity and learning outcomes. There has been much research in the field of technology-assisted tutoring, from Individual Education Plan (IEP)-focused tools to Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS), and this paper seeks to unify many of these themes for the purpose of evaluating LLMs in a pedagogical environment.

The main findings of this paper serve to position AI tools in a special education context, where its unregulated use amounts to a crutch for general education students that may harm content retention and learning development. Handing non-disadvantaged students AI tools may result in the atrophying of the mental faculties. There is a well-established and US Federally-protected system for building technological solutions into IEPs, and in the absence of other regulations it is the opinion of the author that these protocols can be leveraged to protect both differently abled and non-differently abled students from potential dangers of AI.

This paper is organized as follows: a literature review (Section 2) of ITS, tutoring effectiveness, engagement propensity and LLMs in academic applications among other relevant topics provides context for the results of the study. Section 3 describes the study design as approved by the University's Institutional Review Board (IRB). Section 4 discusses the data used in the study as well as high-level demographic information related to the Bentley University student population. Empirical results along with statistical robustness tests (Section 5) are followed by a discussion of implications and limitations (Section 6).

2. Literature Review

Previous systematic literature reviews on Higher Education and online learning reveal a gap that while data-retrieval using popular internet tools dominates campus research behaviors, “little

evidence is available on how students' skills related to online information use can be fostered in [Higher Education], particularly through instructional interventions" (Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia et al., 2021, p. 2004). In algorithmic scans of the available literature, much of the existing body of work relates to data analytics while tutoring-related applications have suffered either from a lack of inclusion of AI-related technologies or from interferences that "still need to be removed or improved for future study" (Jing et al., 2023, p. 11). The field also features geographic congestion with the People's Republic of China accounting for ~40% of adaptive learning publications over the last two decades (Jing et al., 2023, p. 15). This paper looks to address these gaps by first detailing the intersection of internet-based learning outcomes, the relatively young field of AI-supported tutoring, industry-supported findings and other relevant pedagogical variables.

2.1 Internet technology and success

One-to-one support has been known to be extremely effective in contemporary pedagogical assistance ever since the groundbreaking 1984 work that found "the average student under tutoring was about two standard deviations above the average of the control class" (Bloom, 1984, p. 4). The degree to which technology can support this effort has been put under the pre-AI spotlight most recently via the COVID-19 pandemic, where solutions to facilitate distance learning produced at-best mixed results.

The COVID-19 pandemic saw mass adoption of virtual learning technologies in the educational space, but research has continually shown that online venues suffer from low engagement. Even when accounting for 'shopping period' behavior in online courses, dropout rates among regular participants with asynchronous engagement in mathematically oriented fields

can approach 50% (Rieber, 2017, p. 1302). Emphasis on remote learning compared to in-person has also produced evidence of deeply negative and long-lasting mathematics skills consequences in K-12 education that maintain significance when controlling for social and community factors (Domina et al., 2022; Halloran, Jack, Okun, & Oster, 2021). In the post-pandemic context of relatively low-outcome results in technology adoptions following a period of immense stress, AI should be viewed critically in the educational arena as opposed to adopting an ‘any progress is good progress’ mindset. Luckily, there is a large existing body of research related to technologically-enhanced tutoring processes.

2.2 Intelligent tutoring systems

ITS are heralded as tools for potentially expanding education access for millions, and for their myriad customization benefits. In empirical studies related to professional-oriented online learning platforms with associated AI-powered tutors, students who benefited from ITS were shown to achieve learning results “2 to 2.5 times higher...compared to online learning platforms without personalization and active learning” (St-Hilaire et al., 2022, Section 5 para. 2). The benefits of ITS include those associated with the proliferation of smart technology that can provide more data related to student behavior and outcome-related variables than ever before (Kokku et al., 2018), and create opportunities for supporting learning progression via new levels of personalized learning (Akgun & Greenhow, 2022). In a conceptual framework of AI-powered business communication-focused curriculum, this can include simulations and case study scenario recreations to enhance the authenticity of student learning experiences (Riapina, 2023, p. 4). Many of these processes replicate the experience of industry, where AI can feasibly handle various

business cases to support decision-making (Eulerich et al., 2023; Fernandez et al., 2023; Ochmann & Laumer, 2020; Pessach et al., 2020). There is evidence that AI's ability to handle tasks is mixed in the business setting, with consultant-based work producing varying accuracy results according to an "AI frontier" of job competency while low-level tasks correspond with significant efficiency gains (Dell'Acqua et al., 2023). Though this paper focuses on business curriculum literature relevant to its Finance subject matter, ITS have been applied to a wide range of academic disciplines and have even been shown to yield promising results in religious education environments (Akkila & Abu-Naser, 2018).

There are a variety of benefits to ITS but also important disadvantages that may particularly impact post-pandemic communities. These disadvantages include isolation and the loss of body language and other communication skills that impact both development and the instructor-student relationship (Akyuz, 2020, p. 956). There is also the known risk of "hallucinations" where, due to LLMs running a statistical process to determine the most-likely next-character in a string as opposed to information retrieval, they can produce results that appear correct but are not based in reality. This is acknowledged as a particularly large risk in an AI tutoring environment (Mollick & Mollick, 2023, p. 5).

2.3 Self regulation

It is important to take into account that prior to the rise of LLMs students in higher education were already using various forms of AI support in the learning process, most notably in writing. As questioned in the context of special education but more widely applicable across the Academic Integrity spectrum, "is the use of Grammarly to ensure correct grammar cheating" (Marino et al.,

2023, p. 405)? The proliferation of a variety of AI tools aimed at the education industry over the last decade, in the absence of a clear regulatory environment, has placed the governance burden directly on institutions, faculty and technology providers themselves. Self-regulation is one of the most able of these vectors to police behavior due to the uneven distribution of awareness, training and detection methodologies that institutions and faculty have in navigating new technologies.

OpenAI have themselves discussed the risks and rewards of AI integrations at length. In the academic context, GPT-4 is able to pass a variety of standardized exams³ at the estimated 80th percentile lower bound among test-takers (Eloundou et al., 2023, Figure 1). The potential for significant workforce disruption via LLMs enjoys very wide cultural literacy in the US given the long-running social commentary on the risks of AI from the realm of science fiction, and OpenAI themselves go to great lengths to address these concerns. Various suggestions on implementation standards are proposed by company-sponsored research: “we suggest that at a minimum, safety standards for frontier AI development should include: conducting thorough risk assessments informed by evaluations of dangerous capabilities and controllability.” (Anderljung et al., 2023, p. 3). Though this is hedged to an extent later by the authors with the inclusions of possible defenses during risk assessments, it is affirmed that “risk is often contextual” (Anderljung et al., 2023, p. 25) and thus industry-specific standards are implied as necessary when measuring risk versus reward. Additionally, the potential success of proposed governance regimes is limited given OpenAI’s admissions that the technology in its current state is unwieldy to the point of

³ Exams include the Uniform Bar Exam, AP Macroeconomics, AP Statistics, the LSAT, AP Microeconomics, AP Biology, the GRE Verbal, the SAT Math, AP US History, AP US Government, AP Psychology, AP Art History, the SAT EBRW and AP Environmental Science (Eloundou et al., 2023, Figure 1).

unpredictability, where “reliably controlling powerful AI models’ behavior...remains a largely unsolved technical problem” (Anderljung et al., 2023, p. 13). There is also a question of motivation. Though many AI-enhanced adaptive learning systems (ALS) are being adopted in educational settings, “it is beyond the scope of consideration by the developers of AI-ALS to predict how the students’ scores within the AI-ALS could influence their learning outcomes in a summative assessment...after their training has been completed” (How, 2019, p. 3). Prudence is encouraged whenever a corporation with a profit incentive offers a pedagogical tool, and this performance evaluation gap related to LLM-based learning tools and student outcomes represent this papers’ main contribution to the literature.

2.4 Other factors

Instructor effectiveness is an important variable captured by the scope of this study that stands at the intersection of technology and content delivery. Student success related to instructor enjoys a wide literature but also deep-seated resource support at the institutional and government level: “instructors remain the most critical resource outside the home for student learning. Technology can facilitate a teacher’s effectiveness, but ultimately, any new policies, including technological expansion, are at the mercy of the street-level bureaucrats who implement them” (Brooks & Springer, 2023, p. 2). This is reiterated in the context of business-focused curriculum, where faculty development and training is given priority in terms of successful implementation of AI conceptual frameworks (Riapina, 2023, p. 7).

There are important known differences in learning patterns with different age groups that may affect the applicability of higher education studies on K-12 environments. This does not only

include divergent results within the K-12 age groups of successful outcomes related to calculator use, but also to testing conditions where certain tools are prohibited in different education-level settings (Edyburn, 2003, p. 77).

Privacy concerns also remain a key variable in the implementation of ITS and other AI-related systems where tracking and surveillance may not only encounter regulatory hurdles among protected populations but also lead to issues relating to student autonomy and discrimination in the educational setting (Akgun & Greenhow, 2022, p. 435). There is also a concern relating to access bias and inequality, as K-12 US populations in rural and low-AP offering school districts show evidence of affluent/privileged student subgroup dominance in use of supplemental online material (Hart et al., 2023, p. 27). This is a big concern in the potential for technological solutions to compound, rather than mitigate, known tendencies for social factors like community characteristics to influence important educational outcome variables like parental engagement (Cohen-Vogel, Goldring, & Smrekar, 2010) and school librarian access (Gordon & Cicchetti, 2023; Lance, Kachel, & Gerrity, 2023).

3. Study Design

The “Artificial Intelligence and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education” study design was approved with Exempt status by Bentley University’s IRB (#230904003) under Protection of Human Research Subjects, 45 CFR Part 46.104 [d] (2)(i) on August 4th, 2023. A detailed overview of the study empirical model, design and implementation framework follows.

3.1 Empirical model

This study seeks to shed light on learning outcomes in an AI context, but also includes variables that are known to influence student success. Each aspect of the model is discussed at-length in this section. The following variables and their associated coefficients for significance testing fall under the scope of the study: the course section's instructor (*PROF*), the tutors the students visited with (*TUTOR*), whether or not a student used general non-Finance tutoring resources (*LEAF*), whether or not a student used Introductory Finance tutoring resources (*LEAF_{FI}*), whether or not a student used tutoring resources that included AI-generated content (*LEAF_{AI}*), Midterm exam grades (*MID*) and Final exam grades (*FINAL*). Categorized tutoring usage is tested for significance against student-specific performance metrics, including outcomes with the change between the Midterm and Final grades (*DELTA*) and the level Final exam grade itself (*FINAL*). Tutoring usage was tested on a binary basis, tracking whether a student availed themselves of relevant resources and specific tutors during the Semester.

For the *PROF* categorical factor, the instructor with the lowest deviation from total instructor average *DELTA* is selected as the reference category. Results are obtained via linear regression with robust standard errors. Robust standard errors are calculated under Hubert-White HC1 variant specifications as implemented in RTM to control for model heteroscedasticity. The primary investigative interest in this study is *LEAF_{AI}*, where significance in the coefficient and impact on the observed student population (relative to other groups segmented by variable classification) is intended to shed light on whether or not AI helps with student outcomes in the Finance curriculum.

3.2 Curriculum overview

The Finance Department introductory course number 118 (FI-118) provided a unique avenue to study learning outcomes in higher education due to its standardized nature and required curriculum status. In the Fall 2022 semester (one year prior to the launch of the study), Bentley University introduced a change in curriculum to incorporate “new core” courses (Bentley University, 2022) which included FI-118. The FI-118 curriculum features relatively low flexibility for faculty in deviating from core learning objectives, and importantly has standardized Midterm and Final exam components that are consistent across all taught sections. The curriculum uses Pearson virtual textbook offerings,⁴ and the Midterm and Final exams are delivered online via Bentley University’s Brightspace learning management system (LMS). The Midterm exam is composed of fifteen questions with seventy-five minutes for completion, with a lockdown browser to limit student access to computer or online resources during the testing period beyond the test screen and integrated Microsoft Excel spreadsheets; the Final exam has the same testing conditions imposed but with sixteen questions. The exams are non-cumulative and the majority of questions are numerically dynamic to enforce academic integrity standards.

There were eighteen sections of FI-118 during the Fall 2023 Semester taught by a total of ten separate instructors (the maximum discrete sections that an instructor taught was three). The primary investigator of the study visited all eighteen classrooms during the beginning three weeks

⁴ The FI-118 online textbook is a combination of the following textbooks, as customized for Bentley University’s curriculum: Keown (2022) & Keown, Martin & Petty (2020)

of class and presented the study opt-in form as per the Informed Consent process. The Informed Consent opt-in form included AI contributions in structure, content and formatting (Exhibit A).

3.3 LEAF overview

The LEAF employed twenty-two student graduate and undergraduate students during the Fall 2023 semester for peer-tutoring services. The LEAF is available to all Bentley University graduate and undergraduate students for tutoring in the Economics, Accounting and Finance disciplines. The LEAF operates on a check-in / check-out basis via tutor-specific quick-response scanning barcodes (“QRs codes”). These QR codes are displayed on every employee’s nametag so that when a student enters the LEAF they check-in with the peer tutor they will be working with. The tutee is prompted via the QR code to enter their tutoring subject of interest for that visit. There are seven visit subject options available as follows: Introductory or Advanced Economics, Accounting or Finance, then General Studying and finally Other (Figure 1). Once the tutoring session is concluded, on the reverse side of the tutor’s nametag is a checkout QR code specific to that tutor. The checkout asks a binary yes/no question “did your LEAF session include Artificial Intelligence (AI) generated content?” followed by a four-star⁵ LEAF visit helpfulness rating⁶ and finally an open feedback section (Figure 2). All forms are linked to specific tutors and display the tutor number at the end of the title message. QR code surveys are managed by Microsoft Forms and

⁵ A four-star survey methodology is employed so as to ensure fidelity of the dataset. An odd-numbered survey result will allow the respondent to select a ‘neutral’ option. This muddies the data, as ‘neutral’ could reasonably either mean ‘no true feelings either way’ or represent disengagement from the survey as a whole. By keeping an even-numbered score, the respondent must reflect either a degree of satisfaction or dissatisfaction and total non-response to the survey is taken as the only disengagement metric.

⁶ Total average Fall 2023 Semester helpfulness ratings statistics for LEAF tutors had a minimum of 3.56, a max of 4.00, a mode of 4.00, and a mean of 3.84 (1 = worst, 4 = best).

are only accessible via devices with wireless internet credentials that correspond to a Bentley University secure account; this allows the LEAF to not only maintain secure University-accessible services but also to map demand to specific courses where tutee demand is matched with course enrollment lists. In standard Microsoft Forms usage queries related to LEAF QR codes, survey Start Time, Completion Time, survey takers' University email address and linked name are all recorded along with questionnaire results.

LEAF tutors represented a diverse cohort with competencies across all three Economics, Finance and Accounting disciplines. The cohort for the Fall 2023 Semester was 36% non-Male, 18% non-Male and non-Caucasian and 68% international. 36% of tutors were graduate-level students with the rest composed of undergraduates. The LEAF was open from 12:30pm to 9:00pm Mondays through Thursdays and from 5:00pm to 9:00pm on Sundays during the regular semester on a walk-in basis.

3.4 Use of ChatGPT-4

Tutors received a one-hour training and setup session for ChatGPT-4 before the start of the Fall 2023 Semester LEAF opening, as well as a University-public standards of use document. This one-page document (Exhibit B) was the main enforcement mechanism for responsible AI use in keeping with the LEAF mission of supporting, and not competing with, the classroom environment. Tutors were specifically required to not use, or promote the use of, the technology either as an information retrieval system that exposed tutees to hallucinations / incorrect answers or as a plagiarism tool. The training and standards of use document were intentionally kept minimal in order to not bias LEAF employees in usage and to allow for creative freedom for tutors

themselves to find new use cases for the technology. LEAF tutors were all given access to ChatGPT-Plus subscriptions,⁷ which included the latest GPT-4 version of the LLM technology and preferential platform access during heavy-demand service interruptions. Tutors were instructed to use the latest version of the technology for all LEAF functions.

There were a variety of LLMs available at the time of the study design, but for reasons related to number of users,⁸ availability of data-controlled access, integration-propensity in the institutional setting,⁹ name recognition and standardization of tutee experience, the Microsoft-OpenAI ChatGPT-4 platform was chosen as the sole AI tutoring-assistance technology. Due to student privacy concerns, tutors were instructed to only use ChatGPT-4 for LEAF purposes with Chat History turned off (“Dark Mode”) so no identifiable information would be either stored in the system or used by Microsoft-OpenAI for LLM training purposes.

3.5 Data gathering methodology

Upon the completion of the relevant exams by all course sections, the Bentley University Academic Technology Center (ATC) was asked to query all FI-118 course section test results via the LMS. The LMS was able to provide exam question results as weighted by course instructor, which were then standardized in such a way that any non-zero question score was equally weighted across all exams. All personal identifying information is held in the University’s secure data

⁷ These US\$20.00 per month subscriptions were processed via refund.

⁸ OpenAI achieved 100 million users within the first two months of the deployment ChatGPT-4

⁹ Bentley University utilizes Microsoft Enterprise technology for a large variety of administrative and academic functions.

storage environment, and identification keys mapping onto anonymized analytical datasets are stored separately from the research set in line with IRB specifications.

Data from tutors on tutee QR code activity is automatically stored in the Bentley University secure environment via Microsoft Forms integration. This data is regularly queried as part of general LEAF Faculty Director operational management. Study-specific information in treating the opt-in population was handled under the same IRB-controlled methodology as examination data, mapping tutee activity onto exam activity via anonymization keys. There was no difference in service or treatment between LEAF tutees opted-in and not opted-in to the study; there was no identification metric for LEAF tutors to use in discerning if a tutee was opted-in to the study or not.

4. Data

A list of variables is presented in Table 1 with descriptive statistics in Table 2.

4.1 Student demographics

Of the total 612 students enrolled in FI-118 for the Fall 2023 Semester, 417 (68.14%) opted-in to the study. There are 408 students in the final dataset (Table 1), the difference being related to mid-semester course drops. The 2027 class, which comprised the bulk of the study, is 41% female, 32% ALANA and 15% international. 15% of this community identifies as Hispanic and 4% identifies as African American, with 23% of the cohort being First Generation college students and 17% Pell Grant recipients. Given the large sample size and the inclusion of all FI-118 sections, the group demographics are taken as representative of the Bentley University freshman population with some known limitations as discussed in Section 6.2.

4.2 Raw vs. Synthetic data

There is a degree of variability in the data, where during both the Midterm and Final exam some instructors did change the weighting of individual questions as a percentage of the total score. This would have the effect of prioritizing certain content instead of having each question be equally weighted with each question worth 6.67% for the Midterm and 6.25% for the Final. In practice this creates two sets of exam data: one where the instructor's weighted methodology is used (*RAW*) and a synthetic one where whether a student achieved a non-zero on the question is treated as an equally weighted full credit score (*SYN*). The effect on the analysis is minimal, but summary statistics (Table 2) and empirical results are displayed for both exam evaluation methods.

4.3 AI during visits

Over the course of the Fall 2023 Semester, LEAF tutors logged 986 visits across all subjects and logged 709 exits (71.91% exit-to-entry). 35.40% of LEAF visits during the Fall 2023 Semester were Finance related, and 15% of total were Introductory Finance (Total Economics and Total Accounting made up 39.45% and 24.54% of LEAF activity respectively). As the LEAF operates on a walk-in basis, tutors can regularly expect to be handling multiple tutees at once and thus there is a degree to which entries and exits can go un-tracked. By making the tracking of AI in the LEAF self-reported by tutees, it minimized the burden on the tutors to manage the check-in / checkout process while they were busy with instruction delivery, but this remains an area of improvement for future studies.

Of the tutees who opted into the study there were 139 total Fall 2023 Semester LEAF visits, of which 46 (33.09%) were related to Intro Finance and 12 (8.63%) included AI-generated content.

This roughly matches total FI-118 population statistics (including opt-ins and non opt-ins), where 31.68% of visits were related to Intro Finance and 11.88% included AI-generated content.¹⁰ The fields $LEAF_{AI}$ and $LEAF_{FI}$ are mutually exclusive in favor of the Introductory Finance tutoring classification.¹¹

5. Results

5.1 General LEAF results

FI-118 students on the whole struggled with the Final exam to a larger extent than with the Midterm (Table 2). There are a number of possible explanations for this, including disengagement from curriculum following strong Midterm results and a lengthier cumulative Final exam. These results manifest in a statistically significant negative coefficient relationship between MID and $DELTA$ (Figure 3). Student $DELTA$ shows a small improvement in scores for students who leveraged the LEAF for generic non-Finance activity over those that did not leverage the LEAF. Populations that did use LEAF tutoring services for Finance-specific activity did see a marked improvement versus the aforementioned two groups (Figure 4) with a +43.42% and +18.55% Raw and Synthetic $DELTA$ respective outperformance of the full sample. Unsurprisingly, the populations that sought LEAF tutoring for Finance coincided with general lower-level Midterm scores (Figure 5). When mapping LEAF demand by $PROF$, the number of students who availed themselves of Finance tutoring services in an instructors' collective course sections showed a

¹⁰ More detailed specifics on non-opt-in LEAF data are confidential to Bentley University for student privacy purposes.

¹¹ In the overwhelming majority of cases, Introductory Finance visits did not include AI. Dual-classification did occur as an outlier, but due to student privacy concerns we cannot discuss this in more detail in this paper. Additional investigation on this topic is recommended for future research.

negative 66.36% correlation with Midterm Raw and Synthetic exam scores for binary data and a negative 44.35% for level data (Table 3, columns 8 and 9). This is all taken to mean that students who needed additional support because of difficulty with material generally were able to seek that support.

5.2 AI results

The use of AI in the tutoring environment coincides with severe underperformance: tutees who engaged with AI-generated content exhibited a -14.70% and -13.25% Raw and Synthetic *DELTA* performance respectively against the total sample (Figure 4). The AI-exposed group was also the lowest performing sub-group in level exam scores in the observed population (Figure 5).

Under linear regression conditions, Introductory Finance tutoring shows a +0.42 coefficient significant at the $p < 0.1\%$ level for Raw data and a +0.17 coefficient significant at the $p < 1\%$ level for Synthetic data; the Introductory Finance results lose significance, however, with robust standard errors. In both the Raw and Synthetic datasets, use of AI in the tutoring environment coincided with significant negative coefficients against both *DELTA* and *FINAL* (Tables 4 & 5, Row 3). Excluding the one Honors FI-118 section and one course section that reported Final exam technology issues had no material impact on the analysis outcome (see Supplementary Material¹²). In all cases, the linear regression model was significant though Synthetic data tended to report more explanatory power. There is evidence of collinearity arising from overlap in classification variables, though variance inflation factor (VIF) analysis shows this to be within acceptable parameters (see Supplementary Material).

¹² Supplementary Material is available by academic request during Pre-Print.

5.3 Instructor results

Subjecting a model including *MID*, *LEAF_{AI}*, *LEAF_{FI}*, and *LEAF* to analysis of variance (ANOVA) testing against a model with the additions of *PROF* shows significance improvement at the $p < 1\%$ level for Raw data and at the $p < 0.1\%$ level for Synthetic data. ANOVA testing between the *PROF*-inclusive model and a model with both *PROF* and *TUTOR* variables shows significant improvements at the $p < 0.1\%$ for Raw and at the $p < 10\%$ level for Synthetic data. Controlling for instruction quality with *PROF* and *TUTOR* shows an increase in model R^2 ; AI results maintain significance in negative coefficient explanatory power on *DELTA* in the Synthetic dataset (Table 6, Row 3 Column 2). Using level scores for the final exam instead of *DELTA* does show generic LEAF tutoring to be significant in both Raw and Synthetic datasets (Table 6, Row 7 Columns 3-4).

There was relatively low variance in *DELTA* among students across individual instructors' course sections compared to that of the total sample (Table 7), corroborating the strong negative correlation between student LEAF visits and *PROF*-averaged Midterm performance (Table 3). This also supports the observed statistical outcomes, where results for an instructor are consistent across their sections.

It is reasonable to infer that quality of tutor impacts student outcomes, as evidenced by significance in some *TUTOR* coefficients (Table 6) and ANOVA-based explanatory power improvements. In mapping tutee outcomes onto specific tutors, while sample size is an important factor to consider, there is no obvious link between AI-usage and student performance (Figure 6). As the LEAF facilitates tutoring in all three business disciplines, tutors who specialized in

Economics or Accounting were not anticipated to be heavily represented in the Finance-specific data. Tutors additionally showed a wide range of engagement with AI. Of the seventeen tutors who logged Introductory Finance activity over the course of the semester, six did not engage with AI during tutoring visits (Figure 6). This reinforces the findings in the analysis by providing comparison points for tutoring activity with and without AI.

The weighting methodology in the linear regressions for *PROF* variables has a large impact on the instructor results, where selecting alternative reference categories produces differing levels of statistical significance and coefficients. Though additional optimizations can be undertaken to fit the *PROF* variables into the model, this avenue of investigation is out of scope for this paper.¹³ However, given the strength-of-fit improvement in including the instructor variables, it directly informs the central AI question of this paper and presents avenues for future research.

6. Implications

There is insufficient evidence to claim that the use of AI causally relates to worse student outcomes, but based on these preliminary results several causal channels are proposed. These mainly relate to propensity for reliance on shortcuts and exposure to risks of bad answers with AI hallucinations. LEAF tutor feedback regarding the use of AI support both of these claims (Section 6.1), but important known limitations in study methodology and scope are detailed as a caveat and can help inform future research (Section 6.2).

¹³ Deeper investigation into tutor AI propensity and other relevant instructor factors are also out of scope for this paper.

6.1 Tutor feedback

After the conclusion of the Fall 2023 Semester for the LEAF, tutors were asked to respond to a voluntary anonymous survey regarding the use of AI. There was a 36.36% response rate among tutors, of which the majority rated ChatGPT-4 “somewhat useful” as a tutoring tool (Figure 7). The tutors additionally commented that while the standards of use LEAF policy was “somewhat restrictive” (Figure 9), negative uses of ChatGPT were pervasive among tutees.

Survey prompt: “Please provide feedback as to how you saw tutees using ChatGPT and other AI products to support their own learning.”

Tutor Answer: “That’s a downside, most tutees, when using AI, would use it for solving simple algebra. And get it wrong most of the time. I do believe it is not being used correctly since it solves math for them and they don't retain the knowledge of how to do it by themselves.” (Table 9, Row 7)

The unfortunate reliance on AI as a cognitive prosthesis in cases outside of a genuine learning disability lends itself to not just abuse, but to the replacement of learning. These results also seem to confirm the risks of AI tutoring where the “uneven knowledge base of AI” produces “serious confabulation risks” (Mollick & Mollick, 2023, p. 4). The path of technological development must be considered, where training an LLM on specific content for-purpose in an educational environment is already achievable and may minimize these risks. The broader problem of the mental crutch, however, lends itself to a disengagement with the learning process and a loss of foundational skills.

An important question in a business-facing curriculum to ask is if employers will be expecting new hires to use this technology, why should a University withhold it? Literacy with new technology is an important skill, but ultimately the question this paper seeks to answer is not related to the virtue of technology adoption but to the utility of AI in building basic skillsets. Employees that are literate with AI but lack skills to use technology in compelling ways or interpret results may be deemed as more at-risk of automation. Technological literacy cannot replace learning outcomes, and future research should further investigate the preliminary evidence presented here that this is happening with rapid adoption of AI in Higher Education environments.

6.2 Limitations

This study intentionally limited itself to the ChatGPT-4 LLM for reasons discussed in Section 3.4. There is scope to study other LLM technologies either as ‘off-the-shelf’ general market products or trained on curriculum-specific datasets. Due to tutoring-related AI activity remaining in Dark Mode in ChatGPT-4, there is no record of specifics regarding use cases. Future research could benefit from University enterprise-level solutions that give investigators more insight into AI tutoring use cases in the field, as well as more in-depth and prolonged training sessions for tutors and tutees on effective use of LLM technology pre-engagement.

The scope of the study is limited in addressing questions related specifically to Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) markers and AI use. Though the population demographics as discussed in Section 4.1 lend themselves to supportive insights in these fields with a very diverse Bentley University cohort, DEI markers were not queried within the opt-in dataset. Furthermore, while the use of AI in the LEAF did show statistical significance for student outcomes, it is unlikely that

further segmenting the dataset at its current size would yield compelling results. A larger study across more students, more disciplines and perhaps more institutions would be better suited to answer questions of bias within AI-related tutoring as it relates to DEI-marked student outcomes. It is additionally a challenge that controlling for student IEPs was out of scope for the study, and it is possible that the dataset includes students who benefitted from one-on-one tutoring provided by University Academic Services. It will be a challenge for future researchers to navigate the associated privacy constraints in conducting a study that controls for the presence of IEPs.

There is the potential to add scope to the study to include propensity scoring, either in further tracking student outcomes or in pre-post design additions. For the purposes of this study, a high level of AI-engagement propensity in the finance curriculum was assumed for two reasons: firstly, Bentley University is a business-focused institution with a high degree of self-selection towards the industrial disciplines captured in the Economics, Accounting and Finance curricula. A general high propensity towards Finance is implied relative to general higher education institutions. This does limit the broader applicability of the study to some extent. Secondly, following the COVID-19 pandemic related-disruptions, a relative high level of engagement with technology platforms is assumed among the general US higher education student population. The latter point should be emphasized as a generally-applicable marker in pre- and post-pandemic population analysis with the exception of non-traditional education formats. Due to Bentley University's new-curriculum implementation window, the Fall 2023 semester included both sophomore and freshman undergraduates. Future studies that benefit from a fully phased-in new

curriculum are not expected to face this limitation, and studies in higher-level curriculum may benefit from propensity-testing methodologies that include declared major and minor.

The findings of the study support the primacy of instructor quality in student outcomes at the Higher Education level, but further analysis of the data to this end is out of scope for this paper. Future research may avail itself of this or similar data depending on either the combination of this dataset with other model covariates in order to isolate instructor value-add (Kim, 2022), or on the replication of broad-based standardized testing across curriculum.

7. Conclusions

There are two competing visions for AI technology to consider as it relates to academia: one is where AI is used as a “Digital Aristotle” (CGP Grey, 2012) to empower every student, regardless of circumstance, with all of the knowledge in the world to achieve their full potential based on individualized tutoring. The other sees algorithmic decision-making preying on human vulnerabilities, treating ‘users’ as ‘product’ and eviscerating the learning process. The evidence of this study does not outright support the latter vision, but it does offer contradictory evidence to the former. Preliminary evidence suggests that AI in its current state is counteracting student success rather than empowering people to achieve better learning outcomes. The problem of delivering a Digital Aristotle seems to lie in the virtues of the underlying concept, not in the quality of the technology, where the more perfect the virtual instructor becomes the more it *hurts* learning outcomes by suppressing engagement. Humans learn well in a human environment, and an Aristotle-quality digital proxy may not be able to compete with the positive or negative effects of

a live instructor's quality. Evidence suggests that more distraction away from traditional human-based content delivery results in worse outcomes for students.

These results contradict evidence from professional education, though the important difference is that in such cases both the maturity and pre-development of basic skills among participants is assumed. As professional educational settings relate to instances where the employee has direct economic stake in the outcome of 'upskilling' endeavors, they should not be seen as a comparison to the Higher Education environment where the teaching of core skills is in progress. As with the early days of the calculator, the fear that students are outsourcing too much of basic skill training to a machine is a common reaction to powerful technology applications in pedagogy that is mitigated by the supposed potential to empower higher levels of learning. With AI, this time seems to be different. With personal computing reaching such heights that functional AI is an observed reality, it is possible that instead of a 'calculator analogy' we should be making a 'pilot license analogy' where students (and perhaps even low-level employees) must demonstrate mastery of certain skills before being handed the responsibility of high-level technology.

It is the recommendation of the author that educators and academic institutions should proceed with implementation of AI technologies in pedagogy only after finding conclusive evidence that these products support, and do not hurt, student success. Such studies must control for instructor quality, which is found to retain significance in AI research settings. In the interim, the available evidence suggests that the presence of AI in higher education does not show signs of helping students, and may in fact detract from the in-person learning experience.

Appendix

Table 1

List of Variables Used in the Empirical Analysis

Variable Short ID	Variable	Type	N
MID _{RAW}	Midterm Exam Raw Grade ¹	Level	408
FIN _{RAW}	Final Exam Raw Grade ²	Level	408
MID _{SYN}	Midterm Exam Synthetic Grade ³	Level	408
FIN _{SYN}	Final Exam Synthetic Grade ⁴	Level	408
DELTA _{RAW}	Raw Grade Change ⁵	First-derivative	408
DELTA _{SYN}	Synthetic Grade Change ⁶	First-derivative	408
LEAF _{AI}	LEAF-AI ⁷	Binary	408
LEAF _{FI}	LEAF-Finance ⁸	Binary	408
LEAF	LEAF ⁹	Binary	408
STUDENT	Student Code ¹⁰	Classification	408
SECTION	Course Section ¹¹	Classification	18
PROF	Instructor ID ¹²	Classification	10
TUTOR	LEAF Tutor ¹³	Binary	22

Notes. (1) Midterm exam grade as recorded by instructor. (2) Final exam grade as recorded by instructor. (3) Midterm exam grade standardized for equally weighted exam questions. (4) Final exam grade standardized for equally weighted exam questions. (5) Midterm-to-Final grade change as recorded by instructor. (6) Midterm-to-Final grade change standardized for equally weighted exam questions. (7) Logged non-Finance visits to the LEAF during the semester that included AI-generated content (0 = no visits, 1 = visits). (8) Logged Introductory Finance visits to the LEAF during the semester (0 = no visits, 1 = visits). (9) Logged non-Finance visits to the LEAF during the semester (0 = no visits, 1 = visits). (10) Randomly generated anonymization code for FI-118 Students opted-in to the study. (11) Randomly generated anonymization code for FI-118 course sections. (12) Randomly generated anonymization code for FI-118 Finance Department course instructors. (13) Logged LEAF tutor activity for students (0 = no visits, 1 = visits) as recorded via generated anonymization code.

Table 2

Full Sample Descriptive Statistics of Student Exam Results

Variable Short ID	Mean	Median	Mode	Skew	Kurt
MID _{RAW}	85.3365	90.0000	100.0000	-1.7153	3.8328
FIN _{RAW}	82.7142	87.5000	93.7500	-1.3557	1.7054
MID _{SYN}	85.4902	86.6667	100.0000	-1.7209	3.6238
FIN _{SYN}	82.8891	87.5000	93.7500	-1.3648	1.7160
DELTA _{RAW}	0.0122	0.0000	-0.0625	14.3954	256.7770 ¹
DELTA _{SYN}	-0.0028	0.0000	-0.0625	5.4047	65.9795 ²

Notes. (1)(2) Distorted by the presence of outliers.

Table 3

Exam results and LEAF demand by instructor

PROF	MID _{RAW}	MID _{SYN}	FIN _{RAW}	FIN _{SYN}	LEAF _{AI}	LEAF _{AI_L}	LEAF _{FI}	LEAF _{FI_L}
885	92.31	92.31	88.10	92.31	1	1	1	1
412	91.76	91.76	84.56	94.51	1	1	1	2
945	89.67	89.67	90.27	89.33	0	0	3	3
356	87.27	87.27	75.85	87.27	2	2	2	3
436	86.42	86.42	91.01	86.67	0	0	0	0
333	85.10	85.10	74.51	86.01	1	1	1	2
257	83.96	83.96	80.42	84.15	1	2	3	4
58	83.73	83.73	81.73	83.73	1	2	3	19
567	81.44	81.44	87.94	82.27	0	0	4	5
595	78.18	78.18	77.95	76.98	0	0	4	7

Notes. Ranked by MID_{RAW}. LEAF_{AI_L} and LEAF_{FI_L} refer to Level as opposed to binary variable type (i.e. total number of student LEAF visits versus number of students who logged a classified visit over the course of the Semester).

Table 4

Linear regression results for reduced model (excluding instructor variables):

$$DELTA = \beta^0 + \beta^1 LEAF_{AI} + \beta^2 LEAF_{FI} + \beta^3 LEAF + \beta^4 MID + \varepsilon$$

	Full Dataset (RAW)	Full Dataset (SYN)
β^0	1.2643* (0.554)	0.8055*** (0.2039)
$LEAF_{AI}$	-0.2451· (0.1318)	-0.1982* (0.1007)
$LEAF_{FI}$	0.3425 (0.3186)	0.1243 (0.1251)
$LEAF$	0.0787 (0.0511)	0.0506509 (0.0308)
MID	-0.015* (0.0065)	-0.0096*** (0.0024)
R^2	0.2376**	0.2967***
Observations	408	408

Notes. Model R^2 results with robust standard errors are tested for significance under Wald chi-squared parameters. Variable coefficient results are listed as variable name. Results in parentheses denote standard errors. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; · $p < 0.10$.

Table 5

Linear regression results for reduced model (excluding instructor variables):

$$FINAL = \beta^0 + \beta^1 LEAF_{AI} + \beta^2 LEAF_{FI} + \beta^3 LEAF + \beta^4 MID + \varepsilon$$

	Full Dataset (RAW)	Full Dataset (SYN)
β^0	35.3735*** (4.6983)	34.4431*** (4.4978)
$LEAF_{AI}$	-11.7362· (6.0341)	-11.9996· (6.3194)
$LEAF_{FI}$	-1.7299 (4.2669)	-2.204 (4.3166)
$LEAF$	2.8974 (2.3005)	3.0014 (2.3643)
MID	0.5536*** (0.0518)	0.5658*** (0.0498)
R^2	0.2637***	0.2783***
Observations	408	408

Notes. Model R^2 results with robust standard errors are tested for significance under Wald chi-squared parameters. Variable coefficient results are listed as variable name. Results in parentheses denote standard errors. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; · $p < 0.10$.

Table 6

Linear regression results for full model (including instructor variables):

	DELTA _{RAW}	DELTA _{SYN}	FINAL _{RAW}	FINAL _{SYN}
β^0	1.173** (0.4138)	0.7473*** (0.1711)	35.4547*** (5.1476)	33.5003*** (5.0265)
LEAF _{AI}	-0.4599 (0.3065)	-0.288 (0.1581)	-8.2603 (7.7448)	-8.079 (7.867)
LEAF _{F1}	1.0216 (0.8787)	0.344 (0.3326)	-6.6143 (7.015)	-6.2147 (6.9229)
LEAF	0.0278 (0.1937)	0.0667 (0.0884)	10.4714* (4.3527)	9.7456* (4.4148)
MID	-0.0145** (0.0051)	-0.0093*** (0.002)	0.5325*** (0.0527)	0.5546*** (0.0517)
PROF ₅₈	0.0601 (0.0778)	0.0349 (0.0541)	1.2334 (3.6335)	2.2922 (3.4964)
PROF ₃₃₃	-0.0479 (0.0607)	-0.075 (0.049)	-6.0471 (3.5943)	-6.5087 (3.5737)
PROF ₃₅₆	-0.0815 (0.0617)	-0.0641 (0.0425)	-5.279 (2.9313)	-5.2303 (2.9064)
PROF ₄₁₂	0.0891 (0.0851)	0.0364 (0.0572)	1.4054 (4.3005)	-0.0406 (4.4195)
PROF ₄₃₆	0.1574* (0.0654)	0.1477*** (0.0394)	8.993* (3.1423)	10.6891*** (3.0257)
PROF ₅₆₇	0.2827* (0.1169)	0.1778*** (0.0529)	9.4485*** (2.5693)	9.2133*** (2.5144)
PROF ₅₉₅	-0.0606 (0.0786)	0.0042 (0.0492)	0.3163 (3.1301)	1.3212 (2.9897)
PROF ₈₈₅	0.1276 (0.0797)	0.0759 (0.0413)	3.2736 (2.8007)	3.6249 (2.7805)
PROF ₉₄₅	0.1129* (0.0478)	0.0906** (0.0341)	6.4432* (2.6024)	6.563* (2.585)
TUTOR _{Alpha}	-0.2329 (0.2006)	-0.1896 (0.1074)	-15.568 (7.9673)	-15.8328* (7.9303)
TUTOR _{Echo}	-1.0515 (0.8279)	-0.4247 (0.3255)	-4.7554 (7.3815)	-6.0331 (7.4489)
TUTOR _{Foxtrot}	-0.252 (0.5498)	0.0203 (0.2481)	-3.9934 (6.393)	-5.4963 (6.3159)
TUTOR _{Golf}	-0.1108 (0.4348)	-0.0777 (0.197)	-9.7837 (6.3758)	-9.2976 (6.5006)
TUTOR _{Hotel}	0.0073 (0.2024)	-0.0314 (0.0975)	-5.2245 (5.5194)	-5.8969 (5.3494)
TUTOR _{India}	-0.008 (0.1591)	-0.0028 (0.0745)	-3.2549 (5.4075)	-1.6915 (5.5014)
TUTOR _{Juliet}	0.4192 (0.3425)	0.1508 (0.137)	-0.0961 (4.2258)	-0.1662 (4.2412)
TUTOR _{Kilo}	-0.3244 (0.2703)	-0.1288 (0.1092)	-2.2343 (3.5404)	-1.5985 (3.6757)
TUTOR _{Lima}	0.5124	0.3441	4.0083	6.6291

	(0.418)	(0.1933)	(7.8495)	(7.9737)
TUTOR _{Mike}	-0.5428 (0.4828)	-0.1995 (0.1848)	2.1137 (4.5244)	1.5733 (4.6014)
TUTOR _{November}	0.7281 (0.432)	0.5218* (0.2108)	35.7107*** (9.3894)	35.371*** (9.7142)
TUTOR _{Papa}	-1.2733 (0.839)	-0.5649 (0.3191)	-14.0663* (6.6528)	-12.5489 (6.8601)
TUTOR _{Quebec}	-0.5519 (0.5664)	-0.1229 (0.214)	10.432 (6.4858)	10.4827 (6.3809)
TUTOR _{Tango}	0.8101 (0.8408)	0.1672 (0.3233)	-14.2742 (7.3231)	-14.4924* (7.1192)
TUTOR _{Victor}	0.3325 (0.3396)	0.1173 (0.1318)	-5.0615 (5.1869)	-3.8199 (5.6637)
TUTOR _{Whiskey}	-0.0688 (0.1909)	-0.0224 (0.0663)	-3.4647 (7.4657)	-1.9087 (8.0938)
R ²	0.384*	0.4134***	0.3884***	0.4115***
Observations	408	408	408	408

Notes. Model R² results with robust standard errors are tested for significance under Wald chi-squared parameters. Variable coefficient results are listed as variable name. *TUTOR* variable list omits Bravo, Charlie, Oscar, Romeo and Uniform for lack of data, and Sierra for collinearity. Results in parentheses denote standard errors. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; • $p < 0.10$.

Table 7

Variance of DELTA for courses, grouped by PROF

PROF	RAW	SYN
All Courses	0.0062	0.0067
333	0.0053	0.0053
257	0.0022	<0.0000
595	0.0011	0.0025
356	0.0006	0.0006
945	0.0005	0.0006
567	0.0002	<0.0000
412	NA	NA
885	NA	NA
58	NA	NA
436	NA	NA

Notes. “All Courses” refers to total sample *DELTA* variance. *PROF* variables correspond to *DELTA* variance for each instructors’ combined courses. “NA” refers to instructors with only one FI-118 course section for the Fall 2023 Semester.

Table 8

Post-semester anonymous (voluntary) LEAF tutor feedback poll results

	Please provide feedback as to how you used ChatGPT-4 to support your LEAF tutoring.
Answer 1	I pulled up a few examples to understand the concept and reiterate it
Answer 2	For some understanding of concepts that I was struggling with to support my explanation to the tutees.
Answer 3	I did not use ChatGPT to support my tutoring.
Answer 4	I used ChatGPT-4 for R studio code, for making practice problems, and for asking general questions about economics concepts.
Answer 5	* Create examples for students to use. * Explain concepts to me that I had not covered in class so that I could better explain them to students
Answer 6	mostly formula related or the concept with was unknown to me or slightly blur on my memory.
Answer 7	I generated problems for a couple of tutors with it.
Answer 8	I used to find supportive examples to teach specific concepts and, at times, create exercises related to those concepts.

Notes. See Figures 7-10 for quantitative survey results. Feedback was collected via Microsoft Forms. Note that all data is as recorded, including original typos and informality of language.

Table 9

Post-semester anonymous (voluntary) LEAF tutor feedback poll results

	Please provide feedback as to how you saw tutees using ChatGPT and other AI products to support their own learning.
Answer 1	They researched related concepts to learn more about what the question required them to do
Answer 2	To clarify questions
Answer 3	Tutees frequently, when told that we will not just give them the answer to a question, use ChatGPT or other AI products to get the answer on their own. Most of the time, it is the correct answer.
Answer 4	Tutees will often just plug a homework question into ChatGPT.
Answer 5	I did not see tutees using ChatGPT or other AI products
Answer 6	not sure
Answer 7	That's a downside, most tutees, when using AI, would use it for solving simple algebra. And get it wrong most of the time. I do believe it is not being used correctly since it solves math for them and they don't retain the knowledge of how to do it by themselves.

Answer 8 I have seen some of them using ChatGPT to get a roadmap for problem-solving and concept explanation. I have also observed others using ChatGPT to directly obtain answers, questioning whether the solution is correct or not.

Notes. See Figures 7-9 for quantitative survey results. Feedback was collected via Microsoft Forms. Note that all data is as recorded, including original typos and informality of language.

Welcome to the LEAF! (21)

Happy to help you!

Hi, Chase. When you submit this form, the owner will see your name and email address.

* Required

1. Which course(s) are you here for today? *

- Economics (Intro)
- Economics (Advanced)
- Accounting (Intro)
- Accounting (Advanced)
- Finance (Intro)
- Finance (Advanced)
- General Studying
- Other

Submit

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Figure 1. Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance general tutee check-in form. Sign-in is only possible via devices using secured Bentley University wireless credentials.

Thank You for Visiting the LEAF! (21)

Your responses are much appreciated.

Hi, Chase. When you submit this form, the owner will see your name and email address.

* Required

1. Did your LEAF session include Artificial Intelligence (AI) generated content? *

Yes

No

2. Please rate the helpfulness of your LEAF visit (4 stars = most helpful).

☆☆☆☆

3. Let us know if you have any comments or feedback about your visit!

Enter your answer

Submit

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This content is created by the owner of the form. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner. Microsoft is not responsible for the privacy or security practices of its customers, including those of this form owner. Never give out your password.

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Figure 2. Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance general tutee checkout form. Sign-out is only possible via devices using secured Bentley University wireless credentials.

Figure 3. Midterm-to-Final exam performance delta ($DELTA$) on y-axis measured against Midterm level exam result on x-axis. Excludes one outlier.

Figure 4. Midterm-to-Final exam performance delta (*DELTA*) by Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance (LEAF) tutoring usage classification. “Generic Tutoring” refers to recorded non-finance LEAF activity, and “Finance Tutoring” specifically refers to logged Introductory Finance LEAF activity.

Figure 5. Midterm and Final exam performance level scores by Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance (LEAF) tutoring usage classification. “Generic Tutoring” refers to recorded non-finance LEAF activity, and “Finance Tutoring” specifically refers to logged Introductory Finance LEAF activity. Note that level results under-represents positive achievement.

Figure 6. Full-sample student *DELTA* by Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance (LEAF) tutor with corresponding employee AI usage during tutoring visits (anonymized). Ranked by *TUTOR*'s corresponding $DELTA_{RAW}$ average.

Figure 7. Post-semester anonymous (voluntary) Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance (LEAF) tutor feedback poll results for question: “How useful did you find ChatGPT-4 as a tutoring assistance tool?” N=8. Data collected via Microsoft Forms.

Figure 8. Post-semester anonymous (voluntary) Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance (LEAF) tutor feedback poll results for question: “How useful do you believe tutees found ChatGPT-4 as a tutoring tool?” N=8. Data collected via Microsoft Forms.

Figure 9. Post-semester anonymous (voluntary) Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance (LEAF) tutor feedback poll results for question: “How restrictive did you find the LEAF AI Policy to be as a usage guideline?” N=8. Data collected via Microsoft Forms.

Exhibit A

Bentley University Lab for Economics,
Accounting and Finance

AI Pilot Survey
Fall 2023

Informed consent

The Bentley University Lab for Economics, Accounting and Finance (LEAF) is conducting a pilot project to survey the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for the Fall 2023 Semester and to gain insight into their relationship with student academic outcomes.

The data collected will be used solely for research purposes. Any data collected will be kept confidential. Your data will be anonymized to protect your privacy. By providing your consent to this agreement via signature, you will be voluntarily participating in this research project. There is no penalty, academic or otherwise, for not agreeing to participate in this research project. No data collection will be performed by AI during the study.

- 1) Data Collection. I understand that the University will collect my academic performance data for Fall Semester sessions of FI118.
- 2) Use of Data. I understand that the collected data will be used only for research purposes aimed at improving the ability of the LEAF to help students and improve educational resources, methods, and outcomes. The investigators hope that this research will improve the educational experience at Bentley University and may publish their findings to inform improved educational practices elsewhere.
- 3) Confidentiality. I understand that all information collected from me for this study will be treated as confidential research information and will be protected to the extent permitted by law. Reports of this research will include only aggregate data. There is a small risk to the confidentiality of the data collected for the study. To minimize this risk, I acknowledge that the data will be anonymized by removing my personal identifiers from the data collected and that any unique codes or keys linked to my identity will be securely stored separately from the research data.
- 4) Withdrawal of Consent. I am aware that I may withdraw my consent to participate in this data collection at any time and have my data removed from the study without jeopardizing my relationship with the LEAF, my course grade or my relationship with Bentley University in any way.
- 5) Storage of Data. I am aware that my anonymized data will be stored on University systems and may be retained for a period of 7 years or longer if required by the university or publishers. Best efforts will be made to destroy the data after that time.
- 6) Rights and Questions. I understand that my decision whether or not to participate in this study will have no impact on my relationship with the LEAF or with Bentley University. Any queries I have about the study, or my rights as a participant, can be directed to Dr Chase C. Cicchetti (see reverse page).

By signing below, you confirm that you are above the age of 18, that you have read and understood the above statements, and that you willingly give your consent for the University to collect, analyze, and store anonymized academic performance data for research purposes.

Print Name

Sign Name

Date

This document includes contributions from Microsoft OpenAI ChatGPT-4.

Exhibit B

Bentley University Lab for Economics,
Accounting and Finance

Artificial Intelligence Tutoring Policy
Fall 2023

Utilizing Artificial Intelligence in a LEAF Tutoring Environment

This document is intended to help ensure that student tutors use Artificial Intelligence in an effective, ethical, and transparent manner, respecting both student confidentiality and the academic principles upheld by Bentley University. ChatGPT-4 and other Artificial Intelligence platforms (collectively referenced in this document as "AI") can be powerful tools for enriching the tutoring experience, but it is essential to use them responsibly and ethically. Always prioritize the safety, academic growth and well-being of the students you tutor.

1. Confidentiality:

Always operate AI within Bentley University's secure cloud environment or use approved platforms in 'dark mode' where usage data is controlled (i.e. where chat history is not used to train the AI model). Personal, sensitive or confidential student information should never be shared in an AI environment. This ensures the utmost protection of student information and confidentiality.

2. Academic Integrity:

Under no circumstances should AI be used to complete student assignments or facilitate students in doing so. Our role is to guide, inform, and foster understanding, not to do the work for students.

3. Educational Content Creation:

Utilize AI to generate relevant educational content, such as practice problems or illustrative examples. Content should address specific conceptual needs identified in students.

4. Level Appropriateness:

Ensure the content or assistance provided through AI is level-appropriate. Tailor the complexity and depth of material to suit the academic level and understanding of the student being tutored.

5. University Principles and Values:

All interactions, content, and guidance provided using AI should align with Bentley University's principles and values.

6. Transparency:

If you are using AI to create or modify content for student tutees, be upfront about it. Students have the right to know the sources and tools being used in their educational journey.

7. Respect Faculty Policies:

Some departments and/or faculty may have specific policies or guidelines related to the use of AI in the classroom or for assignments. Be aware of, and respect, these guidelines when offering tutoring assistance.

8. Evolving Use of AI:

This document and Lab AI policies may change depending on University guidance or other considerations. Be aware of and adhere to changes in LEAF policy regarding AI as the University continues to evaluate this technology

This document includes contributions from Microsoft OpenAI ChatGPT-4.

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